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Dear reader,

What an inspiring, energetic, and motivating time the last few months have been! We presented our **ontologies collection** during our first annual meeting and in addition, we are very happy to announce that our **English homepage** is up and running! More exciting news? We have a **new member** we would like to introduce to you.

You can read about these news and get more updates in our newsletter below! We hope you enjoy reading it,

Your NFDI4Cat management team

Ontology collection

What are ontologies? How can they be used? Why are they so important for managing research data? NFDI4Cat has launched an ontology collection to help you answer all these questions. Our ontology collection provides a guide with the basic steps to get you started and helps you find the appropriate existing ontologies for your catalysis research.

Ontology Collection

Let's take a look!

NFDI4Cat website now available in English

The NFDI4Cat website was launched earlier this year with the aim of facilitating communication with all international partners. We will provide all important information in both English and German, including not only who and what NFDI4Cat is, but also important results and tools of the project.

[Go to the website!](#)

NFDI4Cat welcomes Dr. Michael Geske

We are pleased to announce the appointment of Dr. Michael Geske as successor to Dr. Ralph Krähnert. Dr. Geske will work on the task area "Data Analysis, Quality Management and Reuse". We are convinced that he will be an excellent addition to our team, as research data management is his favourite topic and his scientific experience will be invaluable. Would you like to learn more about him?

[Yes, I do!](#)

Jahrestreffen Deutscher Katalytiker - postponed

The "Jahrestreffen Deutscher Katalytiker" (German Catalysis Meeting) started as a small meeting to discuss important results and cooperations among German catalysis researchers. Nowadays, this conference is one of the most important events in the catalysis community. Due to the current pandemic situation it was decided to postpone the conference to June 27-29, 2022. Don't forget to register!

[Let's register](#)

NFDI4Cat - Book recommendation

Studies in Analytical Reproducibility: the Conquaire Project

Philipp Cimano, Christian Pietsch, and Cord Wiljes

This book documents eight case studies that describe the efforts and challenges of reproducing analytical results. The lessons learned over more than three years are summarised here, laying out important do's and don't's.

[I want to read it!](#)

Events

FCCAT 2022: French Conference on Catalysis on May 30, 2022 - [Register here](#)

Workshop: FAIR Research Data Management "Basics for Chemists" on April 4, 2022 - [Register Here](#)

NaWuReT-YounGeCatS-Summerschool on May 22 - 25, 2022 - [Find out more](#)

Imprint

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